

Thermochemical Energy Storage at High Temperature via Redox Cycles of Mn and Co Oxides: Pure Oxides versus Mixed Ones.

Alfonso J. Carrillo¹, Javier Moya¹, Alicia Bayón¹, Prabhas Jana¹, Víctor A. de la Peña
O'Shea¹, Manuel Romero¹, José Gonzalez-Aguilar¹, David P. Serrano^{1, 2}, Patricia Pizarro^{1, 2*}
and Juan M. Coronado¹

¹*IMDEA Energy Institute,*

Avenida Ramón de la Sagra, 3, Parque Tecnológico de Móstoles, 28935,

Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

²*Department of Chemical and Energy Technology, ESCET, Rey Juan Carlos*

University, Tulipán s/n, 28933, Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

*Corresponding author: patricia.pizarro@imdea.org

Phone: +34-91-7371155, Fax: +34-91-7371140

Abstract

Development of thermal energy storage (TES) systems for concentrated solar power (CSP) is essential in order to match a variable electricity demand with an intermittent energy source supply, enhancing energy generation dispatchability. The high energy storage densities and the possibility of working at higher temperature ranges make thermochemical heat storage (TCS) via reduction-oxidation (redox) cycles of metal oxides a promising concept for energy storage. For this purpose, manganese and cobalt oxides have been selected as feasible candidates due to their favourable thermodynamic properties. In order to explore the potential of these materials, the capacity of both pure (Mn_2O_3 and Co_3O_4) and mixed oxides ($\text{Mn}_{3-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_4$) to withstand several charge-discharge cycles was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis. Results showed better cyclability for the mixed oxides with low Mn content ($x \geq 2.94$) and, specially, for the corresponding pure oxides, confirming that these materials may be a viable option for TCS.

Keywords: Thermal energy storage; Thermochemical energy storage; Concentrated solar power; Redox cycles; Metal oxides

1. Introduction

The increasingly growth in energy consumption and the environmental concerns due to global warming have caused an enormous interest in the electricity generated by renewable sources. Among them, concentrated solar power (CSP) technologies, with an installed capacity of 1760 MW in 2011, are focused on the production of electricity from concentrated solar energy using thermodynamic cycles (for example, Rankine cycle). The incorporation of thermal energy storage (TES) systems plays a major role in the development of CSP plants since it improves the dispatchability of power plants using solar energy. Storing the thermal energy when the solar resources are abundant and using it during the off sun hours allows electricity generation capable to be adjusted to the variable electricity demand [1].

Thermal energy can be stored as sensible, latent or thermochemical heat [2,3]. Thermochemical heat storage (TCS) presents higher energy densities than sensible or latent heat, and it can be used at higher temperature ranges [4]. This type of thermal storage consists of three steps: charge, storage and discharge. During the charge, the energy provided by the sun is used to perform an endothermic reaction. The reaction products are stored and finally used during the discharge step in order to recover, through an exothermic reaction, the stored energy, which will be used in the power block to generate electricity complementing the solar contribution [5].

Presently TCS has been tested at pilot scale [6], whereas sensible storage systems (using molten salts, steam or thermal oils) are already implemented in commercial CSP

plants [2]. Several reactions have been proposed for TCS applications, including gas-gas, liquid-liquid [7–9], or gas-solid [9] reaction systems. Recently, a gas-solid system based on de/rehydration reactions of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CaO}$ has been investigated in more detail [4,10–12].

An alternative in gas-solid TCS systems consists of using reduction-oxidation (redox) reactions of metal oxides [11,13,14]. Hence, the charging stage is based on the reduction of the metal oxide by heating at elevated temperatures, with the consequent release of oxygen. The discharge stage proceeds by oxidation of the previous product releasing heat. The high temperatures at which redox reactions of some metal oxides take place are able to achieve high operating temperatures, which are expected to be attained in becoming central receiver technologies (600 - 1000 °C). These conditions, that will enhance the efficiency of CSP plants and, thus, reduce the electricity cost, are above the stability range of the currently used molten salts. A second advantage is the use of air as reactant, which is also the heat transfer fluid (HTF) that can be directly driven from the central receiver. This fact will avoid the need of storing the gas as it happens for hydroxides or carbonates-based TCS processes.

Several factors are important regarding the choice of the metal oxide for TCS via redox cycles: thermodynamics, energy storage density, material costs, reaction kinetics, toxicity and the cycling behavior [11]. Various oxides (e.g. Fe_2O_3 , Co_3O_4 , Mn_2O_3 , Mn_3O_4 or CuO) were analyzed by Wong et al. [14] using thermodynamic calculations and experimental analysis in order to study its capability as TCS material. Some of them were rejected because no re-oxidation was appreciable; the temperature range did not match the operating conditions, or the materials presented high cost or slow kinetics. Among

those which were suitable for TCS applications, Co_3O_4 showed the best re-oxidation kinetics. Recently, Co_3O_4 has been used to test a solar-heated rotary kiln as reactor for TCS [15]. Mn_2O_3 was also analyzed by Wong et al. [14] showing an improvement of the re-oxidation by doping the material with second oxides. Both oxides are eligible for the temperature range 600 -1000 °C, so they would fit perfectly the operation conditions of CSP plants provided with a volumetric air central receiver. These oxides store and release energy through the following redox reactions:

Co_3O_4 presents a high potential for TCS based on redox cycles due to its superior energy storage density. However, its toxicity and cost suggest a combination with less harmful and inexpensive metal oxides may be advantageous. This is the case of manganese sesquioxide, which is less harmful and expensive than Co_3O_4 , although it presents a lower energy storage density. Thus, a study of the thermochemical storage performance of oxides that combine both metals seems relevant, as it could result in an economic and efficient material for this application. In addition, as it has been previously reported [14], doping of these redox materials may be a route to modulate other relevant parameters, such as the cycling stability or the temperature of oxidation and reduction reactions. Manganese and cobalt mixed oxides have been investigated for various applications, like electrodes [17] coatings [18] or catalysts, in processes such as CO

hydrogenation over nanometric spinel-type oxides [19], or n-hexane oxidation over Mn-Co oxides [20].

In this study, it has been evaluated the capacity of Mn_2O_3 , Co_3O_4 and their corresponding mixed oxides to withstand repetitive redox cycles and the factors that affect to their stability, as cyclability is a crucial property regarding the choice of the oxide for energy storage in CSP plants.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials preparation

Manganese and cobalt pure and mixed oxides, $\text{Mn}_{3-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_4$, were synthesized by precipitation, varying x from 0 to 3. Solutions of manganese and cobalt precursors were prepared dissolving $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma Aldrich) in deionized water (Milli-Q). After stirring the solution during 30 minutes, the precipitates were formed when 50 ml of ammonia (2.5 M) were slowly added drop by drop to the Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} solution with continuous stirring. When the addition of the ammonia was finished, the solution was aged during one hour and, afterwards, the obtained solids were filtered and washed with distilled water several times and finally dried at 80 °C overnight. The dried material was ground to fine powders using an agate mortar and calcined at 700 °C under static air for 4 h using a heating rate of 2 °C min^{-1} .

2.2. Materials characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were carried out employing a Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$) at a scanning rate of 0.2° s^{-1} . The crystallite size was determined from the most intense reflection, according to the Scherrer formula. Cubic lattice parameter was measured applying the Bragg law and the relation $d^2 = a^2 / (h^2 + k^2 + l^2)$, where h , k and l are the Miller indexes of the Bragg plane, a is the cell parameter and d the interplanar spacing. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) was determined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption analysis at 77 K applying the multi-point BET method using a Quantachrome QuadraSorb-S equipment. Degasification was carried out at 250 °C in vacuum. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken with a Hitachi TM-100 microscope without any previous treatment of the samples. The chemical composition of the synthesized materials was obtained by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), using a Perkin Elmer Optima 3300 DV equipment. Samples were previously digested in acid media in an Anton Paar Multiwave 3000 microwave. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken using a Philips Tecnai 20T microscope. Samples were previously dispersed in acetone and sonicated for 5 minutes. Particle size distribution was obtained by statistical analysis of TEM micrographs with the free-access image processing software ImageJ [21]. For each sample more at least 250 particles were measured.

2.3. Redox cycles analysis

Stability of redox cycles was monitored by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a SDT Q-600 from TA Instruments. In cyclability studies, samples of manganese-cobalt oxides were placed into 90 μl alumina crucibles and subjected to 5 thermal cycles. Each

cycle consisted of a heating step from 500 °C to 1000 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ and a cooling step from 1000 °C to 500 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ under an air flow of 100 ml min⁻¹. Around 25 mg of material were employed for each assay. In order to study the evolution of the surface area after the thermal cycles, a larger quantity of material than the obtained after the TGA redox cycles was needed. Thus 4 redox cycles were carried out in a muffle furnace under a dynamic air flow of 100 ml min⁻¹, using the same temperature profile. After the last cycle, the specific surface area (S_{BET}) was determined as described before.

2.4. Heat flow analysis

Heat release and uptake was measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) with a TGA/DSC/1100 from Mettler-Toledo. Samples were subjected to one heating-cooling cycle under the same conditions as for TGA. Alumina crucibles of 70 µl of capacity were used without any cap. Similar amount of material as for TGA assays was loaded in each analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure and morphology of the Mn and Co-based oxides

The chemical composition of the $\text{Mn}_{3-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_4$ samples, determined by ICP-OES, is presented in Table 1. Special attention has been paid to the preparation with low-doping level (< 10% Me, with Me = Co or Mn) for both manganese or cobalt oxides.

The XRD results, plotted on Figure 1, show that Co-doped manganese oxides presented cubic Mn_2O_3 phase (ICDD 00-041-1442) after calcining at 700 °C, except for the sample with $x = 0.25$. This was mainly constituted by Mn_2O_3 and presented a minor contribution of tetragonal Mn_3O_4 phase (ICDD 00-008-0017). This mixture of Mn_2O_3 and Mn_3O_4 phases is in agreement with the Co-Mn oxides phase diagram reported by Aukrust and Muan [22]. Mixed oxide with $x = 1.41$ content is composed by a mixture of cubic MnCo_2O_4 (ICDD 00-023-1237) and tetragonal Mn_2CoO_4 (ICDD 01-077-0471) spinel type structures. This mixture of F3dm cubic and I41/amd tetragonal spinels has been previously reported for materials of similar compositions [23,24].

Figure 2 depicts the XRD results corresponding to the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 materials. All of them presented cubic Co_3O_4 structure (ICDD file 01-080-1533) with no contribution of other crystal phases.

The crystallite size and the lattice parameter comparison for the different samples are displayed in Table 1. Co-doped manganese oxides showed a similar crystal size and a small decrease on the S_{BET} value while increasing the Co content, except for the material with $x = 0.25$, which did not follow the same trend and presented larger crystallite dimensions. On the other hand, Mn-doped cobalt oxides exhibited larger crystal sizes as the amount of manganese is decreased. In this last case, the variation of S_{BET} values showed the opposite trend, decreasing from 10.3 to 3.1 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ when the crystal size increases from 35 to 66.2 nm, respectively, as expected for nano-particulated oxides.

The structural analysis from XRD results showed that the cubic lattice parameter a is 9.410 and 8.077 Å for pure Mn_2O_3 and Co_3O_4 , respectively, which is in accordance with the lower ionic diameter of Co^{3+} cations [$r_{\text{Mn}^{3+}} = 0.0645$ nm (high spin); $r_{\text{Co}^{3+}} = 0.0545$ nm (low spin) [25]]. For Mn-rich oxides, this parameter decreased while incorporating more cobalt. This fact could confirm that cobalt cations are substituting the manganese cations in the Mn_2O_3 lattice. Similarly, it can be deduced that Mn^{3+} are substituting the Co^{3+} cations in the case of samples with Co_3O_4 cubic phase since the cubic lattice parameter is progressively increasing as the concentration of the former cation is higher.

The morphology of the materials can be described as formed by aggregates of primary particles, which is typical of metal oxide powders prepared by precipitation and subsequent calcination. In the SEM micrographs shown on Figure 3, it can be observed that Mn-based oxides presented rounded aggregates, while Co-based showed a plate-like morphology. The size distribution of the primary particles was determined by statistical analysis of TEM micrographs, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. The results revealed a variation of the particle size, d_{50} (median value), with the dopant content. For the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples, the particle size increased with the amount of Co introduced, except for the $x = 0.25$ sample, which presented a lower value than the pure Mn_2O_3 sample, and with less uniform size distribution. The largest particle size was detected for the $x = 1.41$ sample ($d_{50} = 234.1$ nm). In the case of Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples (Figure 5), the particle size showed a clear decrease with a more homogeneous distribution when increasing the quantity of dopant. In all cases, the particle dimensions were higher than the crystallite sizes determined applying the Scherrer equation, although the relation crystallite size-

dopant amount showed a similar trend. This fact suggests that primary particles are polycrystalline.

3.2. Study of the cyclability

As equations 1 and 2 describe, redox cycles imply a release and an uptake of oxygen, with a consequent mass variation. This variation of weight with temperature for five successive cycles is shown on Figures 6 and 7, for materials with low and high cobalt content respectively. The curves of weight variation versus temperature result in hysteresis loops that give information about the cyclability of each material over the 5 charge-discharge cycle analysis.

Co-doped Mn₂O₃ materials

Doping Mn₂O₃ with Co (Figure 6) caused remarkable changes in its cyclability as the amount of added cobalt was increased. Wong et al.[14] pointed out that, with no addition of a secondary oxide, re-oxidation of Mn₃O₄ was not fully completed. However, in this work, even on the 5th cycle re-oxidation was completely fulfilled for the material without Co-doping (3.37 % of weight gain, very close to the 3.38 % theoretical value according to equation 1), with fast reduction and re-oxidation reactions.

In contrast, increasing the cobalt content, even in small proportions ($x = 0.02$ and 0.05), causes the slowdown of the re-oxidation step, achieving the total conversion during the heating stage (charge) of the next cycle. For instance, the sample prepared with $x = 0.02$ exhibited 93 % of the total re-oxidation during the cooling (discharge) of the 4th cycle and it was during the heating stage (charge) of the 5th cycle where the 100 % (3.38 % of weight gain) was completed. It can also be appreciated that, submitting the oxide to a

new redox cycle resulted in an even slower re-oxidation process, probably caused by the grain growth of the particles due to sintering processes that will be discussed later. This behavior could be extrapolated in a loss of cyclability with time, but longer assays should be carried out to confirm this point. The slowing down in the re-oxidation step is even more pronounced for the material with $x = 0.05$, as evidenced by the progressive spreading of the weight gain curves at low temperature with each cycle. For example, only 84 % of re-oxidation was achieved during the cooling phase of the 4th cycle.

Doping affected also to the temperatures at which the reactions occurred. This is shown in Table 2, where initial and final temperatures, as well as the reaction duration, for both reduction and oxidation steps are compared for the 3rd cycle. The temperature at which re-oxidation started decreased while increasing the amount of Co (768 °C for $x=0$; 746 °C for $x=0.02$ and 723 °C for $x= 0.05$); but the more important difference happened in the final temperature, as for $x= 0.02$ and $x=0.05$ the reaction finished on the heating phase of the next cycle, being re-oxidation a 4-fold slower process. For these two samples, XRD analyses after the 5 redox cycles (Figure 8) showed the presence of tetragonal Mn_3O_4 phase as consequence of the uncompleted re-oxidation on the last cycle.

Concerning the reduction reaction, the results reveal that increasing the Co amount caused a descent in the reduction temperatures, similarly to re-oxidation. The temperature at which reduction started showed a significant variation (from 928 °C for $x=0$, to 863 °C for $x=0.05$), while the final temperature stayed in the same range for both materials. That means that increasing the quantity of dopant also made reduction a

slower process, fact that can be appreciated on the less steep slopes that weight loss curves of Co-dope materials presented.

It is clear that, for these Co-doped manganese oxides; re-oxidation is the slowest process, whose kinetics is associated with the diffusion of oxygen into the oxide structure. A possible way to achieve complete re-oxidation could be increasing the reaction time using slower cooling rates [14].

Increasing the cobalt content up to 8.3 % ($x = 0.25$) produced a significant change in the cyclability of the system. As it has been indicated, this sample is formed by two phases: $(\text{Mn,Co})_2\text{O}_3$ and a minor contribution of $(\text{Mn,Co})_3\text{O}_4$. Initially, the TGA data showed a weight loss of 3.05 %, value lower than the theoretical due to the presence of $(\text{Mn,Co})_3\text{O}_4$, which it is attributed to the reduction of the $(\text{Mn,Co})_2\text{O}_3$ phase to form $(\text{Mn,Co})_3\text{O}_4$. This was confirmed by the X-ray pattern of the material after the 5 redox cycles that displayed a single phase of tetragonal Mn_3O_4 (Figure 8). As expected, according to the observed tendency, the reduction reaction was slower than for the previous samples ($x \leq 0.05$). In this case it started at 630 °C, and finished at 936 °C. After this first reduction the material did not show re-oxidation and consequently no later reduction occurred. This lack of reactivity could be assigned to a thermal stabilization of the Mn_3O_4 caused by the presence of divalent cobalt cations in its lattice.

The sample with $x = 1.41$, which presented a mixture of cubic and tetragonal Mn-Co spinels, did not show any weight change (WG) associated with reduction or oxidation processes, and it was just observed a small weight loss of 0.6 % due to adsorbed water and other compounds removal. According to the phase diagram reported by Aukrust and

Muan, this material should be heated up to more than 1400 °C to see the total reduction of the cubic spinel phase into (Co,Mn)O phase [22]. This suggests that the spinel structure stabilizes the oxidation states of both metals in the temperature range used.

In summary, reduction and, above all, re-oxidation kinetics were not improved by doping with Co, as it tends to thermally stabilize the manganese oxide ($0.02 \leq x \leq 0.25$), producing a negative effect on the cyclability of the material. Therefore, although Co-doping has a certain positive effect of narrowing the temperature difference between oxidation and reduction, overall this chemical modification is not positive for improving the characteristics of Mn_2O_3 as TCS material. In fact, for the five cycles assayed, the sample without Co doping ($x = 0$), showed a perfect cycle stability, demonstrating its suitability for TCS applications.

Mn-doped Co_3O_4 materials

The shape of redox hysteresis cycles for the mixed oxides with high cobalt content differs widely from those containing low concentrations, as it can be appreciated on Figure 7. Reduction initial temperatures were below 914 °C, while oxidation final temperatures were above 812 °C. According to these results, cooling down to 500 °C was unnecessary, but for sake of comparison all the synthesized materials were assayed in the same conditions.

All samples demonstrated high cycle stability and fast oxidation and reduction kinetics in a narrower temperature range as compared with the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples. Co_3O_4 cycle stability over 100 cycles was previously reported by Hutchings et al. in air, who measured the cyclability of Co_3O_4 to produce pure oxygen [26].

Weight loss and gain are close to the theoretical value (6.64 % according to equation 2) for the pure Co_3O_4 sample. For $x=2.97$, the weight variation on its first cycle was 6.60 %, value consistent with the amount of dopant. However the other two samples with Co_3O_4 cubic structure did not reach the theoretical WG value. In both cases it is noticeable that re-oxidation occurred in two steps: first a soft weight increment up to temperatures close to 900 °C, and afterwards a faster re-oxidation. According to Aukrust and Muan phase diagram [22], there is a region between $(\text{Co,Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ and $(\text{Co,Mn})\text{O}$ regions, where both phases coexist. Therefore, if the maximum temperature reached during the reduction was not high enough to enter this region, $(\text{Co,Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ would not be completely transformed into $(\text{Co,Mn})\text{O}$ and a small proportion of the cubic spinel phase will be also present. Accordingly the weight loss will be lower than expected considering the reaction stoichiometry, as it happened in both cases. Thus, the formation of two phases due to the partial reduction could explain that re-oxidation occurred in two steps.

Sample with $x=2.94$ presented a WG of 6.47 %, close to the 6.51 % WG, which this sample should present due to its manganese content, indicating that complete reduction to $(\text{Co,Mn})\text{O}$ takes place at about 1000 °C for this material.

For $x= 2.79$, which has a weight gain of 4.85 % on the first cycle (theoretical WG for this sample is 6.17%), heating up to temperatures above 1000 °C would be necessary to complete the reduction. This was confirmed by performing five consecutive redox cycles following the same temperature program but heating up to 1100 °C (not shown here). In that case the weight loss associated with the first reduction is 6.04 %. Although this value

is close to the theoretical limit, it confirms that heating above 1100 °C is needed to achieve a complete reduction.

Another remarkable difference of the sample with $x = 2.79$, compared with the other Co-rich mixed oxides, was found when studying the XRD after the 5 redox cycles (Figure 9). As re-oxidation of CoO reached the total conversion on the cooling phase, X-ray patterns of these materials presented cubic Co_3O_4 as single phase, except for $x = 2.79$, which exhibited the contribution of other phase. This phase matched with ICDD card 01-080-1545, pattern that also corresponds to cubic Co_3O_4 structure, but with a larger lattice parameter. This could mean that there is a segregation of part of the Co_3O_4 containing a higher concentration of Mn^{3+} substituting cations, thus showing an enlargement of lattice parameter as a consequence of the Mn^{3+} larger radius. This segregation could have been produced due to the thermal treatment that the material suffered during the redox cycles assay.

The 100 % Co sample presented the lowest reduction and re-oxidation temperatures (Table 2). According to Bordeneuve et al [23], the weight loss is related to the reduction of the Co^{3+} cations that occupy the octahedral sites in the Co_3O_4 structure. When manganese precursor is added in the synthesis solution, the Mn^{3+} cations should partially occupy those places, decreasing the amount of Co^{3+} and resulting in a shift to higher reduction temperatures. This is consistent with the results obtained in the structural analysis that suggested the substitution of the trivalent cobalt cations by the trivalent manganese cations.

3.3. Morphological evolution during redox cycles

As it was mentioned before, one of the probable causes of the slow-down of the re-oxidation reactions of Co-doped Mn_2O_3 materials could be the coarsening of the particles due to sintering processes. It can be appreciated on the SEM micrographs, collected after the redox cycles (Figure 10), that the morphology radically changed, showing a high degree of particle sintering. The same effect was observed by Neises et al. when testing Co_3O_4 in a rotary kiln reactor for several cycles [15]. In our case, both manganese and cobalt rich oxides presented extensive sintering after 5 cycles of thermal treatment.

Sintering is a process associated with neck formation and coarsening of particles. These two phenomena caused a decrease on the specific surface area for each sample as shown in Table 1, where the S_{BET} determined after 4 redox cycles is depicted. It was expected that sintering could affect to the cyclability, specifically decreasing the re-oxidation rate by means of slower oxygen diffusion through the powder, as the materials specific surface decreased and the particles coarsened. Nevertheless, a clear relation could not be inferred for each sample since those materials exhibiting cycle stability presented also a high degree of sintering. This fact could be attributed to the different sintering pathways that can be followed depending on the materials structure, composition and morphology. For instance, the $Mn_{2.95}Co_{0.05}O_4$ sample, which presented a progressive decrease on the re-oxidation rate, showed after the 5 redox cycles (Figure. 10 a) a packed structure formed by coarsened particles as a result of the higher degree of densification suffered after the thermal cycling. The particle densification acted as physical barrier to oxygen diffusion, rendering slower re-oxidation reactions. On the other

hand, the $\text{Mn}_{0.06}\text{Co}_{2.94}\text{O}_4$ sample presented strong sintering but without observing any decrease on the re-oxidation rate in any of the 5 cycles. This result is attributed to the less densified structure observed in the SEM micrograph after the 5 cycles (Figure. 10 b), being formed by coarsened particles with a significant presence of voids among them, which could facilitate the oxygen diffusion inside the material.

In general, Mn-doped cobalt oxides showed better cycle stability than Co-doped manganese ones, with reduction and re-oxidation reactions happening in narrower temperature ranges. It is remarkable that, for Mn-doped Co_3O_4 materials, the 5-cycles redox stability does not seem to be significantly affected by sintering processes as it was the case of Mn_2O_3 materials doped with low Co content.

3.4. Study of the released and absorbed heat

The heat absorbed and released during the first charge-discharge cycle was measured by DSC (Figures 10 and 11). As expected, the heat flow curves showed an endothermic peak during the heating, associated with the reduction of the calcined material. During the cooling, an exothermic peak is appreciated, as a result of the re-oxidation of the reduced form. By integrating both peaks it would be possible to determine and compare the energy per mass stored and released by the synthesized materials, i.e., the energy storage density.

Thermal behavior of the reactions for both pure oxides (eqs. 1 and 2) has been scarcely studied by DSC. Berbenni and Marini [27] measured by this technique (under similar conditions to our assays), the reduction and oxidation enthalpies of the $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3 \leftrightarrow$

Mn₃O₄ redox processes; reporting -123.5 and 120.74 kJ/kg Mn₂O₃ for the direct and reverse transformations respectively. Frischt and Navrotsky, using transposed and high temperature drop solution calorimetry, measured the enthalpy of Mn₃O₄ oxidation to form Mn₂O₃ at 704 °C obtaining a value of 202.7 ± 8.0 kJ/kg Mn₂O₃ [28]. This value is closed to the theoretical value 202 kJ/kg Mn₂O₃ [11,29]. Regarding the Co₃O₄ ↔ CoO redox couple, no DSC measurements of both reactions were found in bibliography. Xu and Zheng [30] and Hutchings et al. [26] measured the cyclic transformation between both oxides by differential thermal analysis (DTA). El-Shobaky et al. also measured the cyclic thermal behavior by DTA and the effect of doping with other metal oxides [31–33], reporting changes on the endo- and exothermic peak areas due to the metal doping. Data of the reaction enthalpy found in literature present values of ~ 200 kJ/mol Co₃O₄ (~ 844 kJ/kg Co₃O₄)[14,15,26,29].

In this work, heat flow was measured for one charge-discharge cycle, in order to compare how doping affected to the heat storage process. Data collected from integrating the endo- and exothermic peaks are illustrated in Table 3. As it can be observed, the enthalpy values obtained by cyclic DSC are lower than the values found in literature, as it was the case of those reported by Berbenni and Marini [27], who also used DSC.

For low cobalt content oxides ($x \leq 0.25$), a descent on the endothermic peak while increasing the quantity of doping is shown. As expected, for $x=0.05$ and 0.25 , no exothermic peak was noticed in the heat flow curve, as the former completed the full re-oxidation on the heating phase of the next cycle and the latter did not show re-oxidation at all. The ratio between the energy released and the energy stored for $x=0$ and 0.02 was

0.49 and 0.55 respectively, although in the case of the latter this ratio is increased due to the descent on the endothermic peak area value.

A similar effect was caused by Mn on the Co_3O_4 materials, as the heat absorbed and released decreased while increasing the Mn content. For instance, adding $\sim 7\%$ of Mn ($x = 2.79$) resulted in a descent of $\sim 36\%$ on the heat released, respect to the pure Co_3O_4 sample ($x = 3$). Nevertheless, the heat released/absorbed ratio for each one of these materials is higher than for Mn_2O_3 phase materials (around 80%).

4. Conclusions

Manganese-cobalt pure and mixed oxides were synthesized by precipitation with ammonia and their redox cycle stability characterized in order to evaluate their suitability as TCS materials. Lattice parameter calculation suggests that, for the materials with $0.02 \leq x \leq 0.025$, trivalent cobalt cations are substituting the trivalent manganese cations on the manganese sesquioxide lattice. For materials with $2.79 \leq x \leq 2.97$, Mn^{3+} is substituting Co^{3+} in the Co_3O_4 lattice. In the case of low cobalt content materials, Co^{3+} substitution resulted in thermal stabilization of the manganese oxide and a progressive loss of cyclability, as the cobalt content is increased. It can be concluded that manganese sesquioxide samples with low Co-doping do not present cycle stability, and thus are not suitable to be a TCS material.

Pure oxide samples ($x = 0$ and 3) showed more constant reduction and re-oxidation temperatures and faster reactions than the doped ones. Albeit doping with $\% \text{Mn} \leq 1.8$ on cobalt oxides did not show a detrimental effect on the cyclability, if compared with Co-

doped manganese oxides, it slightly deteriorated kinetics, reduced the heat stored/released amount and shifted the process towards higher temperatures rendering these doped oxides in a less attractive alternative. Therefore results obtained suggest that operation with pure oxides is more effective for TCS applications. Although the heat released and absorbed values of Mn_2O_3 are far from those obtained with Co_3O_4 , its excellent cycle stability, low toxicity and inexpensiveness still make this material an interesting candidate for TCS applications.

Acknowledgments

The work has received financial support from the projects TCS Power of the FP7 and MULTISTOR (ENE2012-36937) of the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness. Some of the authors thank the financial support of “Juan de la Cierva” (PJ) and “Ramón y Cajal” programs (VPO and JGA).

References

- [1] M. Romero, A. Steinfeld, Concentrating solar thermal power and thermochemical fuels, *Energy & Environmental Science*. 5 (2012) 9234–9245.
- [2] A. Gil, M. Medrano, I. Martorell, A. Lázaro, P. Dolado, B. Zalba, et al., State of the art on high temperature thermal energy storage for power generation. Part 1— Concepts, materials and modellization, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 14 (2010) 31–55.
- [3] S. Kuravi, J. Trahan, D.Y. Goswami, M.M. Rahman, E.K. Stefanakos, Thermal energy storage technologies and systems for concentrating solar power plants, *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*. 39 (2013) 285–319.
- [4] F. Schaubé, A. Wörner, R. Tamme, High Temperature Thermochemical Heat Storage for Concentrated Solar Power Using Gas–Solid Reactions, *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering*. 133 (2011) 031006.

- [5] A.H. Abedin, M.A. Rosen, Assessment of a closed thermochemical energy storage using energy and exergy methods, *Applied Energy*. 93 (2012) 18–23.
- [6] K. Lovegrove, A. Luzzi, I. Soldiani, H. Kreetz, Developing ammonia based thermochemical energy storage for dish power plants, *Solar Energy*. 76 (2004) 331–337.
- [7] S.M. Ramade, M.-C. Lee, H.W. Prengle, Chemical storage of solar energy kinetics of heterogeneous SO_3 and H_2O reaction-reaction analysis and reactor design, *Solar Energy*. 44 (1990) 321–332.
- [8] H. Prengle, J. Hunt, C. Mauk, E. Sun, Solar energy with chemical storage for cogeneration of electric power and heat, *Solar Energy*. 24 (1980) 373–384.
- [9] G. Ervin, Solar heat storage using chemical reactions, *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*. 61 (1977) 51–61.
- [10] F. Schaubé, L. Koch, A. Wörner, H. Müller-Steinhagen, A thermodynamic and kinetic study of the de- and rehydration of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ at high H_2O partial pressures for thermo-chemical heat storage, *Thermochimica Acta*. 538 (2012) 9–20.
- [11] A. Wörner, S. Binyami, F. Giger, J.-B. Soupart, J. Gonzalez-Aguilar, A. Steinfeld, et al., The TCSPower Project Thermochemical Energy Storage for Concentrated Solar Power Plants, in: *Solar Paces, Marrakesch, Maroc*, 2012.
- [12] F. Schaubé, A. Kohzer, J. Schütz, A. Wörner, H. Müller-Steinhagen, De- and rehydration of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in a reactor with direct heat transfer for thermo-chemical heat storage. Part A: Experimental results, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*. 91 (2012) 864–856.
- [13] M.A. Fahim, J.D. Ford, Energy storage using the BaO_2/BaO reaction cycle, *The Chemical Engineering Journal*. 27 (1983) 21–28.
- [14] B. Wong, L. Brown, F. Schaubé, R. Tamme, C. Sattler, Oxide Based Thermochemical Heat Storage, in: *16th Solar PACES International Symposium, Perpignan, France.*, 2010.
- [15] M. Neises, S. Tescari, L. de Oliveira, M. Roeb, C. Sattler, B. Wong, Solar-heated rotary kiln for thermochemical energy storage, *Solar Energy*. 86 (2012) 3040–3048.
- [16] A.R. Armstrong, P.G. Bruce, Synthesis of layered LiMnO_2 as an electrode for rechargeable lithium batteries, *Nature*. 381 (1996) 499–500.

- [17] B. Babakhani, D.G. Ivey, Investigation of electrochemical behavior of Mn–Co doped oxide electrodes for electrochemical capacitors, *Electrochimica Acta*. 56 (2011) 4753–4762.
- [18] W. Wei, W. Chen, D.G. Ivey, Oxidation resistance and electrical properties of anodically electrodeposited Mn–Co oxide coatings for solid oxide fuel cell interconnect applications, *Journal of Power Sources*. 186 (2009) 428–434.
- [19] Q. Liang, K. Chen, W. Hou, Q. Yan, CO hydrogenation over nanometer spinel-type Co/Mn complex oxides prepared by sol-gel method, *Applied Catalysis A: General*. 166 (1998) 191–199.
- [20] S. Todorova, H. Kolev, J.P. Holgado, G. Kadinov, C. Bonev, R. Pereñíguez, et al., Complete n-hexane oxidation over supported Mn–Co catalysts, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 94 (2010) 46–54.
- [21] C.A. Schneider, W.S. Rasband, K.W. Eliceiri, NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis, *Nature Methods*. 9 (2012) 671–675.
- [22] E. Aukrust, A. Muan, Phase relations in the system cobalt oxide–manganese oxide in air, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*. 46 (1963) 511.
- [23] H. Bordeneuve, S. Guillemet-Fritsch, A. Rousset, S. Schuurman, V. Poulain, B. Helene, Structure and electrical properties of single-phase cobalt manganese oxide spinels $Mn_{3-x}Co_xO_4$ sintered classically and by spark plasma sintering (SPS), *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*. 182 (2009) 396–401.
- [24] E. Vila, R.M. Rojas, J.L. Martın de Vidales, O. Garcıa-Martın, Structural and thermal properties of the tetragonal cobalt manganese spinels $Mn_xCo_{3-x}O_4$ ($1.4 < x < 2.0$), *Chemistry of Materials*. 4 (1996) 1078–1083.
- [25] R.D. Shannon, Revised effective ionic radii and systematic studies of interatomic distances in halides and chalcogenides, *Acta Crystallographica Section A*. 32 (1976) 751–767.
- [26] K. Hutchings, M. Wilson, P. Larsen, R. Cutler, Kinetic and thermodynamic considerations for oxygen absorption/desorption using cobalt oxide, *Solid State Ionics*. 177 (2006) 45–51.
- [27] V. Berbenni, a. Marini, Oxidation behaviour of mechanically activated Mn_3O_4 by TGA/DSC/XRPD, *Materials Research Bulletin*. 38 (2003) 1859–1866.
- [28] S. Fritsch, A. Navrotsky, Thermodynamic Properties of Manganese Oxides, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*. 79 (1996) 1761–1768.

- [29] T. Mattisson, A. Lyngfelt, H. Leion, Chemical-looping with oxygen uncoupling for combustion of solid fuels, *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*. 3 (2009) 11–19.
- [30] Z.P.Z. Xu, H.C.H. Zeng, Thermal evolution of cobalt hydroxides: a comparative study of their various structural phases, *J. Mater. Chem.* 8 (1998) 2499–2506.
- [31] G.A. El-Shobaky, N.M. Ghoneim, I.M. Morsi, Thermal behaviour of cobaltic and cobaltous oxides as influenced by doping with some alkali metal oxides, *Thermochimica Acta*. 70 (1983) 325–337.
- [32] G.A. El-Shobaky, N.M. Ghoneim, I.F. Hewaidy, I.M. Morsi, Thermal stability of cobalt oxides doped with V_2O_5 and MoO_3 , *Thermochimica Acta*. 61 (1983) 107–119.
- [33] G.A. El-Shobaky, N.M. Ghoneim, Effects of BeO-doping on the thermal behaviour of cobalt oxides, *Thermochimica Acta*. 89 (1985) 63–74.

List of figures

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction patterns of the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples ($0.00 \leq x \leq 1.41$) after calcination. \diamond Mn_3O_4 (00-008-0017), \bullet MnCo_2O_4 (00-023-1237), Δ Mn_2CoO_4 (01-077-0471).

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples ($2.79 \leq x \leq 3.00$) after calcination.

Figure 3. SEM images of the samples (A) $\text{Mn}_{2.95}\text{Co}_{0.05}\text{O}_4$ and (B) $\text{Mn}_{0.06}\text{Co}_{2.94}\text{O}_4$ after calcination.

Figure 4. Particle size distribution histograms of the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples ($0.00 \leq x \leq 1.41$). On the top-right part of each histogram is depicted an example of the TEM micrographs used for the study.

Figure 5. Particle size distribution histograms of the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples ($2.79 \leq x \leq 3.00$). On the top-right part of each histogram is depicted an example of the TEM micrographs used for the study.

Figure 6. Redox cycles (% weight vs temperature) of the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples ($0.00 \leq x \leq 1.41$). (For the sake of clarity the temperature range below 450°C is not shown).

Figure 7. Redox cycles (% weight vs temperature) of the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples ($2.79 \leq x \leq 3.00$). (For the sake of clarity the temperature range below 450°C is not shown).

Figure 8. X-ray diffraction of the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples ($0.00 \leq x \leq 1.41$) after 5 redox cycles. $\diamond \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4(01-080-0382)$.

Figure 9. X-ray diffraction patterns of the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples ($2.79 \leq x \leq 3.00$) after 5 redox cycles. $\diamond \text{Co}_3\text{O}_4(01-080-1545)$.

Figure 10. SEM images of the samples (A) $\text{Mn}_{2.95}\text{Co}_{0.05}\text{O}_4$ and (B) $\text{Mn}_{0.06}\text{Co}_{2.94}\text{O}_4$ after the 5 redox cycles assay.

Figure 11. First cycle DSC curves of the Co-doped Mn_2O_3 samples ($0.00 \leq x \leq 1.41$). The arrow indicates the cycle direction.

Figure 12. First cycle DSC curves of the Mn-doped Co_3O_4 samples ($2.79 \leq x \leq 3.00$). The arrow indicates the cycle direction.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

